

8 Theory, QFT and General Relativity: Synthesis toward a Grand Theory of Everything

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Abstract:

Analysis for three leading theories, the newborn 8 theory, which predicted the fine structure constant, and an infinite succession of coupling constants with decreasing magnitude alongside an equation of dark energy, is compared to the major leading theories of the past century. In a search for a complete synthesis. Each framework will be analyzed according to its strengths and weaknesses.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.13)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.14)$$

It also predicts negative time invariant acceleration around areas of extremum curvatures, given no data is available from the first three terms.

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad - \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.15)$$

Weakness

The 8-Theory is still a newborn, despite its stunning predictions of the fine structure constant and description of dark energy, it needs additional experimental validity. Achieved when the fifth force of nature will be discovered at magnitude of $\frac{1}{850}$ relative to the strong interaction. Experimentalists have not yet found such a Boson. They should find such a field if they were able to detect a much weaker interaction as gravitational waves.

The author does not include the pattern of the masses, as he is not sure regarding the correctness of the equation. That is an additional weakness of the framework. The thesis suggest to variations of the masses equation, which differ by a numerical factor of nine. We should find a fourth family of quarks below first generation. Experimentalists have not yet detect such a family.

Quantum field Theory

There is no need to specify the strength of the framework, which is its overwhelming accuracy in prediction of certain traits, such as the magnetic moment of the electron, its visual appeal using the Feynman diagrams, and the combination of QM with relativity by ensuring phases will be independent from the amplitudes. Without a doubt, Quantum field theory stand as one of the most remarkable achievements of the human race. Possibly will never be thrown by her power of precision.

QFT weaknesses – four Points to Consider:

The simplicity of the claims versus the complexity of notation – take for example The statement of the conservation of energy, or the fact that the rules are invariant Under shifting frames, the equations are long, complicated, and tiresome to work With and hard to understand as well.

Dependency upon frames of reference – any fundamental theory of physics will not even consider frames of reference, as they do not affect the underlying principles governing everything. 8-theory does not consider any frames of reference, so it is a major advantage.

Artificial insertion of operators of matter, these must be inserted, but overall in nature these things happen in natural and spontaneous way. In The 8 theory those perturbations Accrue natural way and are allowed, there is no need to insert any operators. These must take the form of matter by the first equation and our mathematical proof. Overall, we can combine the two frameworks; they do not contradict each other as far as one can see. 8-Theory can create simplifications in QFT framework, and QFT Framework on 8-Theory may yield new stunning predictions in agreement with what we know.

A final theory must be simple and accurate. QFT is extremely accurate, not simple notation wise. It does not involve gravity, while 8 theory should find the coupling constant of gravity In the endless series of coupling constants. If so, it is a unified theory in which QFT is a higher liar data set – an additional mathematical tool for matters of probability.

There is no data or explanation to the point of singularity, why did it happen and how? There is also no explanation for dark energy and dark matter consisting the major part action in the universe. These questions are within the domain of explanation of the 8T.

General Relativity

8T is in partial agreement with the GR. As we can conclude from the main equation the equivalence principle between gravity and acceleration, there is an agreement there. However, there is also a main difference. The 8T regard fermions as arbitrary amount of Curvature on a manifold. Those arbitrary amounts vanish in pairs and create threefold Combinations. There is always a chance a net curvature will appear, which is prime, and that was the idea, which yielded the coupling constant series, each prime is a boson propagating from matter.

General relativity regard the cause of gravity to the arbitrary variations vanishing into matter, where no curvature is allowed:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.16)$$

while the 8T proven bosons to be the cause for gravity and in particular to be net curvature extending, a ripple distribution in space, by the theorems which yielded the coupling constants series.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.17)$$

Put another way, how can the graviton meditate the interaction long range if not a single graviton was detected? Einstein theory does not take into account the effect of spin. Gravity has spin two, which indicate short range, and for those reasons, it is incomplete and far from being completely correct.

$$\left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow [(2N(g)) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} \quad (1.18)$$

$$[2N(g) + 2] \rightarrow 2N(g) \quad (1.19)$$

Synthesis

All we need for a fundamental theory of physics is a Lorentz manifold. **That is it.** If we require it to be stationary we have quarks, time invariant acceleration and the series of coupling constants, which represent net variations or net curvature extending outward, these are bosons, which are infinite in kind. We also have infinite families forming, as mass is regarded as variations or curvature converging inward, another possible simplification. The probability of events that can be calculated using QFT framework and the Feynman diagrams, and general relativity is already built in as The 8 Theory and GR both are assembled by the very same ideas – Manifolds and Ricci flow.

String theory is not considered, as it has no advantage of any kind, it deals mainly with trying to predict the exact **motion** of those arbitrary variations that is impossible to do. Nor it is even important, as it do not reason why those things appear in the first place, and the answer is vividly clear in the 8-theory – arbitrary variations take the form of matter. The 8- theory is far superior in predictions and in reasoning. Moreover, it is much simpler. Overall nature is simple; it is our lack of understanding, which causes the complications alongside trying to answer the wrong questions.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)